

FABRICATION OF FRM BAR BY SWAGING

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In order to find a better method of FRM fabrication, aligning short fibers in copper matrix by swaging method was tried. A copper pipe containing steel fibers and copper powder was swaged into 5mm bar with 95% reduction ratio. In the obtained bar steel fibers were well aligned along swaging direction. The fiber volume fraction was dependent on length of fibers and inner diameter of pipe. By changing type of copper powder, length of fiber and annealing temperature, FRM bar with up to 6% fiber volume fraction and up to 45kg/mm^2 tensile strength was obtained. In principle, FRM bar of infinite length may be produced by addition of this method to continuous butt-welding of metal strip into pipe and feeding mixture of fiber and powder into being welded pipe.

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Introduction

In spite of that the fiber reinforced metal (F.R.M.) is believed to be able to improve the properties of metallic materials, so far it is not yet widely applied in industry, perhaps due to the various difficulties such as high material cost of fiber, problems about interfaces between fiber and matrix metal and difficulties in manufacturing method. One of them is the problem of fiber alignment. Many reports have shown theoretically¹⁾ or experimentally²⁾ that even small misalignment of fibers in fiber composite material will cause steep decrease of its strength.

Manufacturing of F.R.M. using continuous fiber seems to be relatively easy, because, in this case, already established manufacturing processes of F.R.P. can be applied. But the manufacturing of F.R.M. using short fibers is not so easy, since the attaining of well alignment of the fibers in metal matrix is very difficult. In this field, only a few methods³⁾ are being proposed and one of them, is a method using extrusion of mixture consisting of fibers and metal powder with or without binder. In this method, such defects may be pointed out, that, at low extrusion pressure, pores will remain in the extruded product and fibers will not well align themselves and, at higher extruding pressure, pores will decrease but fibers will be destroyed. Calow et al.⁴⁾ obtained silver reinforced wire with well aligned Al_2O_3 whisker by extrusion using ammonium-alginate as binder. They couldn't obtain high density product by extrusion only, and it was necessary to add many other complicated processes.

The authors, in order to find easy and simple manufacturing process of high-density F.R.M. of short fiber, tried swaging method, which is similar to extrusion, but by which it is possible to obtain high-density products, as T. Nakagawa et al.⁵⁾ have proved experimentally. Authors tried to manufacture copper bar reinforced with steel fiber by swaging. Steel fiber is being produced commercially for application to automobile tire and is easily available. Fiber reinforced copper may be useful as high-strength conductor.

Experimental

As the F.R.M. to be manufactured by swaging, copper bar reinforced with steel fiber was chosen for the reason as mentioned above. As the container for the mixture of copper powder and steel fiber to be swaged, three sorts of commercial copper pipe with different diameter were used (pipe X: O.D. 18, I.D. 15mm, pipe Y: O.D. 19, I.D. 17.4mm, pipe Z: O.D. 28.5, I.D. 26mm). In order to study the influence of the powder shape, three types of copper powder, that is, -100mesh electrolytic powder (powder A), -325 electrolytic powder (powder B) and -100mesh atomized powder (powder C) were used. Steel fiber of length 12mm, diameter 0.2mm and aspect ratio 60 is commercially made tire cord wire with thin brass coating. Chemical

analysis of it is C 0.70~75, Si 0.15~0.30, Mn 0.5~0.65, and its tensile strength is 280kg/mm².

Experimental procedures are as follows. A certain quantity of steel fiber and copper powder, which had been weighed previously according to the predetermined fiber weight fraction, were mixed by hand on a sheet of paper and the mixture, little by little, was put into a vertically supported copper pipe with the bottom end sealed with soft solder. This pipe containing copper powder and fiber was cold swaged into a smaller diameter bar by a horizontal swager with four dies. Practically in any case, no more swaging than 85% reduction was possible. So the cold work-hardened bars were annealed and again swaged finally into 8mm- or 5mm-diameter bar. Swaging and annealing were conducted through one of the following three different schedule depending on the original diameter of copper pipe.

Schedule 1: 20mm ϕ \rightarrow 12mm ϕ (annealing) \rightarrow 5mm ϕ

Schedule 2: 20mm ϕ \rightarrow 12mm ϕ \rightarrow 8mm ϕ (annealing) \rightarrow 5mm ϕ

Schedule 3: 30mm ϕ \rightarrow 20mm ϕ \rightarrow 12mm ϕ (annealing) \rightarrow 8mm ϕ \rightarrow 5mm ϕ

Work-hardened bars were annealed in a H₂ atmosphere resistance furnace at usually 800°C for 1 hr. Manufactured copper bar was cut into 150mm length specimens and the specimens were tested by an Instron-type tensile testing machine at the strain rate of about 2.5·10⁻²/min. The fluctuation range of the tensile strength among the specimens cut from a single product bar was within 5%. The various sections of the manufactured bar and the fractures were observed by an optical- or a scanning-electron-microscope.

Results and discussions

The results of the tensile test of all the specimens are shown on Table 1. The value of the tensile strength shown on this table is the mean value from two or three specimens made under the same condition.

The effect of fiber weight fraction in mixture

All strength data were shown on Table I. Fig. 1 shows the relation between tensile strength and fiber weight fraction in the mixture of fiber and powder. This graph exhibits that high fiber weight fraction in mixture does not always contribute to strengthen the composite bar manufactured.

To find the reason of this unexpected result, the behavior of the fiber and powder poured into a transparent glass tube was observed. 10g of steel fiber of 12mm length and 90g of copper powder A were put into a vertically supported glass tube of inner diameter 16mm by the same procedure as mentioned. It was observed that the fibers which fell on the bottom of the glass tube did not align themselves, did not fill the inner volume of tube closely but tangled themselves loosely. And all the copper powder fell through

the tangled fibers onto the bottom of tube as shown schematically on Fig. 2. From this observation, it is evident that volume fraction of fiber in a tube does not depend to the fiber weight fraction in mixture of fiber and powder, but to the other factor, that is, the ratio between length of fiber and diameter of tube.

From this observation, authors considered that the unexpected result of the tensile test above mentioned is due to the difference between real fiber volume fraction in product and fiber weight fraction in mixture. According to author's experimental procedure, if the fiber weight fraction in mixture was increased, the fiber volume fraction in product would not increase more than a certain limit value which is determined by the ratio between the fiber length and tube inner diameter.

Fig. 3 shows a longitudinal section of a copper pipe under working by a swager. Copper powder which has fallen onto the bottom of pipe (on the photo, to the left end of pipe) has been pushed by dies and moved through the tangled fibers. At the working zone (left side of the photo), the fibers have aligned themselves along the axis of pipe in copper powder matrix and copper powder particles have been packed densely. At the non-working zone (the right side of the photo), fibers remain as tangled and the copper powder particles which have been pushed from the bottom end of the pipe exist among fibers. It is clearly shown that, as working proceeds, tangled fibers gradually align themselves in copper matrix.

The shape and distribution of steel fiber in copper matrix in a manufactured composite bar is shown on Fig. 4 -a and -b. These photos exhibit that steel fibers are well aligned along the axis of copper pipe and their diameter has reduced to $0.08 \sim 0.12\text{mm}$ from original 0.2mm .

From these photos, it is considered that in the swaging process steel fibers in copper matrix are worked out and the diameter of them is reduced.

The effect of annealing temperature

Fig. 5 shows the tensile strength of the specimens cut from the composite bar made from the same material through the same schedule at the various annealing temperature, that is, 600° , 800° and 1000°C . (Specimen 7~9).

From this figure, it is considered that there is optimum annealing temperature for this swaging method, which may be enough high to soften the work-hardened copper pipe but not too high to maintain the strength of steel fiber.

Fractograph of these specimens is given on Fig. 6. In this photograph, copper matrix exhibits the fracture by plastic deformation. Necking is observed around the fracture of steel fiber and brittle fracture pattern is seen at the central area.

The effect of copper particle shape

Fig. 7 shows the tensile strength of the composite bars made from three types of copper powder and the same fiber and pipe

through the same schedule (Specimen 10~12).

The composite bar made from fine electrolytic copper powder has the highest tensile strength. Comparing the tensile strength of the specimens of same particle size, it is clear that the specimen made from atomized powder is stronger than that made from electrolytic powder. This may be due to the high fluidity of atomized powder. About the effect of particle size, it may be considered that, in finer copper particles, steel fibers will align themselves more easily and remained pore size will be smaller than in coarse particles.

The effect of diameter of copper pipe

In order to study the effect of diameter of copper pipe used, the strength of specimens made from the same fiber and powder using pipes of different diameter is compared. The tensile strength of specimen 14 in Table I (pipe diameter 28mm, final 5mm) is higher than that of specimen 12 (pipe diameter 19.5mm, final 5mm).

The higher strength of specimen made from larger diameter pipe may be due to higher fiber volume density, better alignment of fibers and higher work reduction of fiber in it than in specimen made from smaller diameter pipe.

From the result of experiments above mentioned, it is recognized that swaging method has the possibility to be used for manufacturing F.R.M. bar of short fiber. This method is very simple and easy to be applied for manufacturing composite bar. If the metal pipe is made continuously by butt-welding of metal strip and the mixture is fed into the pipe being welded, it may be possible to manufacture endless composite bar or wire by swaging of the continuously made container pipe.

Conclusion

With the aim to apply swaging method for manufacturing of F.R.M., copper pipes containing short steel fiber and copper powder were swaged into composite bars and the tensile strength of the bars was tested. The results obtained are as follows:

1. In a composite bar made from copper pipe containing copper powder and steel fiber by swaging, steel fibers are well aligned and evenly distributed along the axis of bar.
2. Steel fiber content in the bar seems to be determined by the relation between fiber length and pipe diameter.
3. The selection of diameter of pipe and the particle size and shape of powder is important to obtain high-strength composite bar by swaging methods.

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Table 1: Tensile strength of composite bars swaged from copper pipe containing mixture of steel fiber and copper powder

No.	Pipe		Copper Powder	Fiber Weight Fraction(%)	Schedule	Tensile Strength (kg/mm ²)
	O.D. (mm)	I.D. (mm)				
1	18	15	A	0	1	30
2	18	15	A	5	1	34
3	18	15	A	10	1	45
4	18	15	A	20	1	40
5	18	15	A	30	1	35
6	18	15	A	40	1	31
7	19	17.4	C	10	2	35*
8	19	17.4	C	10	2	42
9	19	17.4	C	10	2	38**
10	19	17.4	A	10	2	37
11	19	17.4	B	10	2	48
12	19	17.4	C	10	2	42
13	28.5	26	C	10	3	31***
14	28.5	26	C	10	3	50
15	28.5	26	C	20	3	32***
16	28.5	26	C	20	3	42

* annealing temperature 600°C, ** annealing temperature 1000°C,

*** measured at 8mm dia.

Fig. 1: Tensile strength of the specimens of various fiber weight fraction in mixture

Fig. 2: Schematic figure of mixture of steel fiber and copper powder which is put into a vertically supported glass tube

Fig. 3: Photograph of a section of a copper pipe with steel fiber and copper powder being swaged

a

b

Fig.4-a: Photograph of a cross section of a composite bar made by swaging

Fig.4-b: Photograph of a longitudinal section of composite bar

Fig. 5: The relation between tensile strength of composite bar and annealing temperature

Fig. 6: SEM fractographs of composite bars of various annealing temperatures

Fig. 7: Tensile-strength of composite bars made from various copper powders

Fig. 8: SEM fractographs of composite bars made from various copper powders